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Orientaciones valorativas de los jóvenes y sus implicaciones para la política social¹

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Resumen. El sistema de valores del individuo y la sociedad se forma a través de un proceso complejo y dinámico, moldeado por características culturales, acontecimientos históricos vividos, educación y otros factores. El artículo identifica a la juventud como un actor clave en el proceso que transforma activamente las normas sociales y los estándares de comportamiento existentes. El estudio identifica las prioridades de valores de la juventud rusa contemporánea en el contexto de la digitalización activa de la sociedad. Se presentan los resultados de una encuesta realizada a jóvenes de educación superior y solicitantes que asisten a eventos de puertas abiertas. Los resultados se agrupan según valores personales, incluyendo actitudes hacia las tradiciones, la expresión de independencia y la participación en actividades para lograr resultados y la comunicación, y se analizan en el marco de la orientación política, de consumo y ética de la investigación. El estudio concluye que es necesario investigar los cambios en los sistemas de valores de los jóvenes para desarrollar una política social relevante y eficaz.

Palabras clave: autoidentificación, sociedad, política juvenil, política social, red social, identidad, orientaciones de valores, familia.

Value orientations of young people and their implications for social work

Abstract. The value system of the individual and society is formed through a complex and dynamic process shaped by cultural features, experienced historical events, education, and other factors. The paper identifies youth as a key player in the process that actively transforms existing social norms and standards of behavior. The study identifies the value priorities of contemporary Russian youth in the context of the active digitalization of society. The paper reports the results of a survey of young people receiving higher education and applicants attending open-door events. The results are grouped according to personal values, including attitudes to traditions, the expression of independence, and engagement in activities to achieve results and communication, and analyzed in the framework of the research's political, consumer, and ethical orientation. The study concludes that changes in young people's value systems need to be investigated to develop a relevant and effective social policy.

Key words: self-identification, society, youth policy, social policy, social network, identity, value orientations, family.

INTRODUCTION

The formation of a value system in the individual and society is a complex and dynamic process that includes many components with a multidirectional impact (Semikin et al., 2021). The typically cited components include the country's cultural values, the values of the given era, the experienced historical events, the features of the education system, the social circle, stance in life, lifestyle, and the age-specific stages of personality development, which affect the axiological basis of the person's worldview (Lewis-Smith et al., 2020; Kodirov, 2021). Scientific articles note that to assess the state of many social processes and model their changes, it is crucial to define the value priorities of young people, which are multidisciplinary (including political science, sociology, psychology, and communication studies) (Leonova & Karpenko, 2020; Semikin et al., 2021; Zvereva & Khvorova, 2022; Jamtsho & Wangchug, 2024).

Value orientations and their distinguishing features are typically studied within different socio-demographic groups, but priority is given to groups including young people (Rubtsov, 2023). This focus is justified by the fact that youth is large in numbers. It reproduces social relations and their structure and transforms existing processes, changing the accepted norms and standards of behavior and ideas about what is important and socially acceptable (Sokolova & Mikhailov, 2022; Apukhtina & Kravchenko, 2023). Because young people experience plenty of events associated with their social status in the system of public relations and self-identification, they represent the most active socio-demographic group that directs changes in behavioral patterns and society's general development.

Over its long history, society has developed universal values that have remained important throughout generations (e.g., freedom, justice, good, truth) (Bobrovskaya, 2019). The fast pace of technological progress set in the 21st century has forced youth to adapt to new conditions of life, which often change in a non-linear fashion (Lewis-Smith et al., 2020). The people of today, regardless of their age and occupation, take advantage of information technologies, digital devices, social

networks, and television. The Internet and television now serve as the main information suppliers, shaping people's value orientations by broadening their outlook (Bobrovskaia, 2019; Mamedova, 2021). Information consumption, no matter the source, is personal, determining the individual's priorities, development, education, and value system (Sokolova & Mikhailov, 2022).

Our study aims to identify the values of youth in the age of active digitalization of a wide variety of processes. The research objectives dictated by this goal were to determine the qualitative and quantitative composition of respondents, develop a criterion-based assessment battery to conduct sociological monitoring and identify the software tools required for it, and obtain and process the results of the monitoring.

The study's theoretical significance lies in its contribution to identifying trends in the value priorities of youth in the context of the changes in the pace of globalization, digitalization, and other cultural transformation processes. Our findings can be applied in an in-depth analysis of identity development in today's youth, providing a foundation for theoretical models to explain young people's behavior, motivation, and preferences.

The practical significance of our research is provided by the opportunity to utilize its results in the field of social policy through the development of more effective programs for adapting and realizing the potential of youth in the context of its needs and transformations considering the varying degrees of influence of socio-cultural and other factors.

METHODS

The study's subject was the formation of value orientations in young people in contemporary Russian society, which is actively transforming under the influence of digital systems and technologies. The objects under study are the methods, means, environment, and subjects influencing the pace of changes within this process.

Under current Russian law, young people are citizens between the ages of 14 and 35. As of 2024, young people account for a quarter of the country's total population (about 37 million people). About 60% of Russian youth live in cities. The number of young families in the country is estimated at 5.3 million, of which 3.9 million have children. The Russian Federation is currently implementing its Youth Policy Strategy, which aims to create conditions for the effective self-realization of young people.

To achieve the research goal, we employed survey methods. The respondent sample included university students and applicants attending open-day events and their companions aged 14–35. The questions presented to the respondents were based on the characteristic value orientations of young people according to S.H. Schwartz's personal values questionnaire. Among these values were tradition (respect for and compliance with society's customs, traditions, and culture), conformity (ability to prevent actions that may harm others), security (achieving safety, harmony, and stability in relationships for others), universalism (reaching understanding and tolerance in different interactions), benevolence (achieving a conflict-free state in interaction both in society and with individuals), power (imposing one's will on others), self-direction (ensuring independence in the choice of ways and means of action for certain purposes), stimulation (the drive to achieve new things), achievement (personal success), and hedonism (the ability to derive pleasure or sensual enjoyment).

RESULTS

Below we briefly describe the main results obtained after systematizing and analyzing the survey.

1. Attitudes to tradition (customs and culture). The younger generation does not purposefully seek to forget the past, but it is difficult for them to perceive or recognize events that have not directly affected them. An additional obstacle is the emergence of many different, sometimes contradictory, opinions on the same events, both among experts and ordinary people, which are broadcast via the Internet, by the film industry, and in video games. This negatively affects the assessment of historical and cultural events, casting doubt on their significance and discouraging their study. Some view the development of the country or society through the lens of striving to match the living standards of other countries and become skeptical of an emotional connection to the past, believing it to impede progress.

Nevertheless, interest in a detailed study or general awareness of historical events and their consequences among today's Russian school students is kept alive by the school curriculum and extracurricular events, which have become popular in recent years.

When answering questions about historical events, school students often cite Conversations about Important Things as their source of information. The Conversations are extracurricular lessons systematically held in the educational organizations of primary general, secondary general, and vocational education since 2022 to strengthen traditional Russian spiritual and moral values and foster patriotism. These 45-minute classes take place each Monday after the mandatory lineups with the national anthem and flag-raising. The Conversations are devoted to a theme depending on students' age and the date (e.g., New Year family traditions of different peoples of Russia, relationships in the family, the Day of National Unity, the electoral system of Russia (30th anniversary of the Central Election Commission), "Russian language. Great and Mighty. 225 years since the birth of A.S. Pushkin", eco-friendly consumption). Furthermore, schoolchildren and university students report taking part (as participants, volunteers, or organizers) in military-patriotic events. One of these is the Immortal Regiment, which is a movement of people who join the annual Victory Day procession through the streets of cities holding photographs of their relatives who fought in the Great Patriotic War, including underground fighters, resistance fighters, home front workers, concentration camp prisoners, blockade survivors, and children of the war. The movement's participants also record family stories about their veteran relatives on the People's Chronicle website). Other examples include the Victory Letter (an international initiative encouraging people to write warm wishes to veterans of the Great Patriotic War and other local conflicts), the Ribbon of Saint George (the participants are gifted the ribbons of Saint George and educated on this symbol of Victory and the courage of the heroes of the Great Patriotic War), the Memory Candle (all-Russian event dedicated to the remembrance of those who lived through the horrors of the Great Patriotic War, as part of which people light candles in the stillness of the night), etc.

Answering culture-related questions, our respondents note that they regularly attend events using the Pushkin Card program. The program aims to popularize cultural events organized by theaters, museums, philharmonics, concert venues, libraries, and art schools among young people between the ages of 14 and 22. Participants in the program can purchase tickets at state expense up to a certain annual limit. The events covered by the program follow the themes of patriotic, spiritual, and moral upbringing of youth, preserving family values, developing creative industries, preserving Russian culture and identity, and pedagogics and mentorship.

2. Self-direction. Adolescence comprises several developmental stages characterized by a significant transformation of moral attitudes and behavior patterns: adolescents wish to be adults and want others to treat them as adults (Lopatina, 2022). Surveys of the relevant age groups confirm this notion. However, answers touching upon the demonstration of responsibility show the respondents' reliance on their parents (e.g., when visiting the polyclinic, buying groceries and goods, solving problems at school, choosing the place of education, etc.), which distorts the notion of personal responsibility. School students do not see the difference between their rights and responsibilities, which hinders the development of social responsibility to society and social institutions (family, school, and state) (Tereshchenko et al., 2025). The survey results demonstrate that this age group has a low level of legal responsibility, meaning they do not know the limits beyond which their action becomes an offense and what kind of punishment they may receive. We hypothesize that the underdeveloped sense of responsibility in adolescents is a result of state education policy over the last decade and the transformation of the family as a social institution. The family has handed over the function of upbringing to the school, while the school lacks effective mechanisms to influence students under current legislation. School students fail to form a realistic perception of social responsibility. Nevertheless, some respondents shape their development trajectory and try to stick to it, recognizing the potential consequences of their actions or inaction.

In the course of university education, attitudes to self-direction begin to transform. A particularly striking difference in responses is observed between students who continue to live with their families and those who move out. This difference continues to grow through the years of study. The survey demonstrates that first-year students are unprepared for the business communication characteristic of the adult environment: they need to independently plan their workload, complete assignments, build connections with peers and professors, solve conflicts, etc. This situation is noted by nearly all respondents from this age group.

3. Achievement. The analysis of responses points to a general trend spanning all age groups of young people: their priority is to achieve career success (to self-actualize and become financially independent) and gain financial prosperity. Although there is nothing inherently wrong with the desire to be well-off and live comfortably, the growing influence of pragmatic and mercantile values on the consciousness of young people can be detrimental to society. The answers demonstrate that respondents' attitudes to labor have changed compared with the results of other sociological surveys in previous periods (Rubtsov, 2023). Most respondents are not ready to move up the career ladder if the promotion comes with increased responsibility and less personal space (free time, hobbies, etc.) and are unwilling to work for the benefit of society without personal gain.

4. Communication. The responses indicate that young people communicate using messengers and put their trust in social networks and information from online resources. Students mention having group chats in messengers, chats with specific groups of people (e.g., by interest, work, place of residence), and individual chats. This fosters less selective attention because of the short messages, the randomness of attention because of the constant switching between messages, etc. Most respondents failed to formulate sentences correctly (making mistakes in punctuation marks and words). This is especially pronounced among students. This situation might be attributed to the lack of regular Russian language and speech culture classes and the use of automatic error correction functions in messengers and text editors.

DISCUSSION

Value systems, regardless of demographic and age groups, have always been subject to investigation in sociology, cultural studies, philosophy, and other humanities (Threadgold, 2020; Mamedova et al., 2022). Of particular interest are the features of the development of value orientations in youth as the group responsible for the country's future socioeconomic development (Barkova et al., 2017; Leonova & Karpenko, 2020; Semikin et al., 2021). Researchers categorize such orientations from the standpoint of political, consumer, and ethical orientation (Zelenkov, 2023; Hockey, 2024). The structure of the conducted research and the use of the questionnaire method in surveys on relevant topics correspond to this perspective.

A.G. Rubtsov (2023: 258) notes that

“in the course of reforms, the ideology of the social significance of labor and labor education was abolished in society. The value of labor per se dropped to zero, and the image of an altruistic worker disappeared from public opinion along with the desire to work inspirationally for the benefit of the Motherland”.

This is confirmed by the survey results: the respondents are ready to work only in the here and now as long as their interests are not violated without considering long-term prospects.

Researchers commonly raise concerns about unquestionable trust in Internet resources (social networks, channels, etc.). M.Iu. Zelenkov (2023: 47) concludes that

“young people do not particularly trust the public and political space, have become more independent in decision-making, and prefer virtual dialogical interaction, thus continuing to destroy the stereotypes of behavior and values of Russian society, which can lead to the decline of its culture”.

Our findings partially support this conclusion. However, not all of our respondents trust Internet resources completely: they cross-check information using different sources and install additional software to reduce the amount of unwanted and harmful content. This result is consistent with the findings of other researchers (Vaniukhina et al., 2019; Ruckwongpatr et al., 2022).

At the same time, “the dominant feature in the formation of value orientations of Russian youth is its social orientation based on traditional family values” (Zelenkov, 2023: 47). This conclusion is supported by the survey results (the development of values related to nobility, respect, and kindness in the family) and the analysis of statistics on the participation of young people in charitable, public, and environmental initiatives (Shamionov, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

Value orientations are important components in every person's life, as they shape their mentality and worldview. Value orientations represent the person's subjective ideas about their goals in life and those of their family, society, and state, which give grounds for assessing one's and others' behavior. The current state of the value system is changing in the context of historical events, the social circle, the educational environment, and family values. This leads us to conclude that the younger generation experiences life events consciously, actively transforming values and priorities.

Our findings emphasize the need to conduct similar studies to monitor the current state of the value system in contemporary youth and analyze the results in the context of interaction between different age and demographic groups. This research will be instrumental in identifying the conditions and mechanisms needed to combat social injustice, negative stereotypes, and persistent social stigmas if Russia continues to suffer from population aging. One promising direction for further research is to explore the phenomenon of a sense of responsibility for oneself and one's identity group or even society. This phenomenon is primarily associated with volunteer movements and ideas that are especially popular among today's Russian youth.

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